

High Density = High Citations? Approaches for Tracking Knowledge Evolution

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Introduction

To study the formation and evolution of knowledge systems, a key aspect is the integration of local and global, individual and systemic knowledge processes (Renn 2020). The explanation of how, for example, a scientific field in the twentieth century emerged — often incorporating thousands of scientists — is a structural endeavour but must be relatable to individual or local micro-histories if one argues for their systemic dependency. We here discuss an approach to tackle this challenge empirically using specific methods developed within the framework of socio-epistemic networks (SEN) (Kaye et al. 2024). The framework is built on the assumption that knowledge is codified through the formation of cognitive, material, and social structures, representable via multi-layered, time-evolving networks (Renn et al. 2016). A SEN therefore comprises three interconnected layers: social, semiotic (or material), and semantic. The methods presented here are primarily focussed on language-based change, i.e. the semantic layer. As an example for the global perspective we use the case of the so-called “Renaissance of General Relativity” (Blum, Lalli and Renn 2020; Will 1989), while taking the works of physicist Hans-Jürgen Treder as an example for the individual perspective. We then look at three different but complementary methods to compare individual trajectories against the development of this global phenomenon to examine the relationship between the development of individual scholars' written works and the evolution of the disciplinary field they work in. In this case, General Relativity and Gravitation (GRG) research. While the results of combining a quantitative view of structural changes with local case studies are necessarily incomplete, we argue that such a quantitative approach can guide the exploration of individual trajectories within the larger picture, making certain aspects of these different individual trajectories comparable to each other.

Data

For recent periods in the history of science, the primary input for the SEN framework typically consists of large sets of (semi-)unstructured texts, such as scientific publications, as well as texts of other forms and provenance. The semiotic/material layer is therefore in most cases the initial one before the construction of the other SEN layers, since information about past events is usually provided by archival materials. In the example we discuss here, we focus on publications related to the field of GRG from 1911 to 2000, aligning our selection criteria with those developed by the project “The Renaissance of General Relativity in the Post-World War II Period” at the Max Planck Institute for the History of Science.⁵⁶ This alignment allows for the integration of our findings with those of the project. To identify authors who wrote in the period 1925-1970 on topics related to general relativity, (Lalli, Howey and Wintergrün 2020) created a set of articles and actors primarily based on data from the Web of Science, which led to 8296 articles in their GRG publication space. In contrast, we employed the Astrophysics Data System NASA/ADS, which

⁵⁶ <https://www.mpiwg-berlin.mpg.de/project/renaissance-general-relativity>. Most of the project's findings were published in the special issue “The Renaissance of Einstein's Theory of Gravitation” and in Alexander S. Blum, Roberto Lalli and Jürgen Renn, eds., *The Renaissance of General Relativity in Context 16* (Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2020).

offered a more comprehensive coverage of GRG, particularly for non-English publications.⁵⁷ We extended the strategy to the year 2000, while using comparable search criteria. Our dataset contains around 160000 publications in total, but for our comparative analysis, starting with Treder's first therein listed publication, we are only interested in those from 1957 onwards (157455 publications). In methods 1 and 2, we analyse the textual content of our documents, which in this case consist of titles plus abstracts translated into English, and in method 3, we utilize the citation data provided by the ADS.

Methods

To examine the diachronic development of individuals versus the global development of this corpus and to analyse (language-based) changes on the semantic layer, we employ three different but complementary methods. By doing so, we investigate whether the tendencies of the results are similar across all methods or if they differ, and if so, in what aspects. The aim of this multi-method approach is to increase the robustness of the quantitative analysis, ideally leading to a more rigorous historical analysis.

1 — Density approach

Firstly, we look at local versus global variations in document embedding densities. Similar to BERTopic (Grootendorst 2022), we start by converting our texts into embedding vectors and reduce their dimensions for better visualization and clustering. We then identify clusters and label them using representative documents from each cluster, resulting in a time-dependent visualization where similar publications are grouped closely. To track changes over time, we apply Kernel Density Estimation (KDE) to analyse density changes around each vector. We calculate KDE in two-year increments, starting with the initial publication year of each document, and only include new publications added in each period, excluding earlier ones. This analysis then shows how the density around each vector changes over time, indicating the relative volume of similar content published or the attention given to related topics. This process allows us to track how the neighbourhood around each document evolves, whether the concentration of similar content increases, remains steady, or decreases. Figure 1 depicts a schematized version of this process for one document. This is applied to all documents in the respective corpus, facilitating a global comparison between individual documents and/or regions over time. By doing this, we can follow the trajectories of individual documents

⁵⁷ Nevertheless, the dataset exhibits the same issues that are common in most bibliographic datasets derived from online repositories, including incompleteness (e.g., full text, citation data), biases (e.g., language/geographic, collection focus), and inaccuracies in translation, among others.

or groups of documents, focusing on either content (topic combinations) or metadata (documents from specific authors, institutions, geographic locations, etc.).

2 — Information theoretical approach

Secondly, we employ an information-theoretic approach developed in computer linguistics (Bizzoni et al. 2020; Degaetano-Ortlieb and Teich 2018), based on relative entropy for the same selection of documents. We again divide the period under consideration, 1957-2000, into time slices of two years. Each of these slices is divided into a small corpus, created out of the publications of the individual, and a large corpus, representing the rest of the field of GRG, created out of all other publications in that slice. Out of the texts of both corpora, we then generate simple unigram language models. These are represented by independent relative term frequencies, i.e. for each time slice we have two distributions of word probabilities. These distributions can be compared by calculating pointwise and overall Kullback-Leiber Divergence (KLD) between them. KLD measures the extra bits required to encode using a non-optimal model. The more bits needed, the greater the difference between the two distributions. For each time slice we plot the divergence values, noting peaks and troughs in the KLD as indicators of significant deviation, and sort the pointwise KLD, identifying the terms that contribute most to the deviation. This helps to detect semantic change, assess its significance, and identify strongly contributing features, enabling us to generate independent but comparable results to the outputs of the first method. Additionally, we calculate pointwise and overall KLD for each interval compared to all other intervals. This diachronic comparison seeks intervals that deviate least and most from a given interval. For example, if the 1990-91 interval from the Treder sub-corpus is most similar lexically to the 1960-61 interval of the main-corpus, one might argue that Treder published on similar topics or used similar language in 1990-91 as the rest of the GRG field in 1960-61.

3 — Bibliometric approach

The third approach utilizes well-established bibliometric methods to control for the results of the other two language-based methods. Using co-citation networks, we track changing patterns to control for the global vector densities and divergences in language use. For that, we compare co-citation networks of individuals against the “mainstream” co-citation networks of their field. Again, we split our dataset into two-year time slices and follow their changes diachronically, aiming to reveal the extent to which an individual's co-citation pattern, or “Citation Identity” (White 2001), develops in comparison to global co-citation patterns, or the “intellectual base” (Chen 2006) of the field. By defining “mainstream” within the network as the most frequent co-citations across the entire network, we compare the created networks by calculating their Jaccard distance for each time slice.⁵⁸ These steps allow us to quantitatively evaluate how closely an individual's citation behaviour mirrors or deviates from that mainstream. The final step is then to examine if and how the perceived trends reflect the behaviour we see for the same individual with the other two approaches.

Case Study

As mentioned above, here we focus on the example of General Relativity and Gravitation (GRG) research. GRG as a field began to form and gain traction only after World War II, following a thirty-year period of stagnation in general relativity research. This revival of interest, termed the “Renaissance of General Relativity” overlaps with Treder's most productive years. We examine this concurrent development from 1957-2000, compare it with other individuals (here Joseph Silk) from the same period, and discuss limitations, problems, and potential other applications. We find that as time progresses, Treder uses language akin to that from the “past”. This correlates with a relative decrease of document embedding density around his publications, i.e. a decline in research activity on the topics he addresses, as well as a decline in citations. In contrast, physicists like Joseph Silk and other highly cited authors use “future” language that shapes the use of language in the field of GRG. Concurrently, research activity around the topics they write about

⁵⁸ Another avenue we want to pursue are Network Embeddings, since they capture not just the presence of connections but their structural and contextual relevance.

increases (densification in embedding space). We can therefore track and compare individual or local trajectories of change within the global field of GRG.

Conclusion and Outlook

From the individual perspective, the hypothesis we aim to test with this combined approach is simplified: if many people write about what you write about (high density), your vocabulary is close to the vocabulary of the mainstream (low KLD), and your intellectual base is close to that of the mainstream (low Jaccard distance), and vice versa. A last step we plan to implement involves tracking direct citations to monitor the development of the reception of individuals within the global setting, potentially answering whether a correlation exists between high density, mainstream language, mainstream citation identity, and high citation count. The method can be transferred to other fields of research and will also be applied in settings beyond the highly formalised scenarios of scientific publications, such as in knowledge dissemination during migration processes or in the transition of knowledge from science to policy.

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